

Enhancing gender equity in succession planning for sustainable growth of SMEs in Tanzania

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Abstract

Gender-equitable succession planning is vital for the sustainability of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Tanzania. This study, conducted in Kahama District, examined gender equity and succession planning practices in 50 SMEs using interviews, focus groups, and questionnaires. Descriptive statistics and Likert scale analysis revealed a strong awareness of gender equity but limited involvement of female family members in succession planning. While over 50% of participants recognized the importance of gender equity, traditional norms continue to favour male leadership. Varied responses on gender roles indicated differing attitudes among SME owners. The study highlights the persistence of gender bias and a general lack of awareness about effective, inclusive succession planning methods. To address this gap, SMEs should integrate gender equity into their strategies through educational initiatives, public awareness campaigns, and financial incentives aimed at fostering inclusive leadership and enhancing the participation of women in business succession.

Keywords: *Succession Plan, Enterprise; Sustainability; Gender Equity; Traditional Frameworks.*

JEL Classification: J16; L26; M13.

1. Introduction

Gender-equitable succession planning is vital for the long-term sustainability and success of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Tanzania. In the context of this study, it refers to the intentional inclusion of both men and women in the processes of identifying, developing, and selecting future leaders, thereby ensuring equal access to leadership opportunities regardless of gender. Despite its importance, gender equity is often overlooked in succession planning practices, resulting in limited diversity and inclusivity within leadership structures (OECD, 2012). The relationship between gender equity and succession planning in SMEs is both significant and multifaceted. Succession planning plays a critical role in enabling smooth leadership transitions and ensuring continuity of operations (Maseda et al., 2023; Monyei et al., 2021). It entails the strategic identification and development of internal talent to assume key leadership roles when current leaders retire or depart. In an increasingly competitive business environment, effective leadership development and succession strategies are essential for maintaining organizational continuity and resilience (WTO, 2020). Nevertheless, there is a notable lack of data on succession planning practices among SMEs in Tanzania, particularly regarding gender equity considerations. Gender-equitable succession planning is essential not only for enhancing the sustainability of SMEs but also for promoting inclusive participation in business ownership and leadership. Recognizing and integrating gender equity into succession strategies is therefore critical for advancing effective SME development, enabling both men and women to contribute meaningfully to the sector's growth.

Notably, gender diversity plays a critical role in succession planning for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), as it promotes equity and inclusive development. Promoting gender equality is not only a matter of social justice but also a strategic business practice that enhances economic performance and aligns with global development priorities. Integrating gender diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) into management education, particularly through service learning, is essential for shaping future business leaders who value inclusivity (Bandyopadhyay, Das, & Mahajan., 2022). Women, in particular, deserve focused attention, as they have historically encountered systemic barriers and continue to be underrepresented in SME leadership. Studies reveal that limited gender diversity in leadership and management education negatively affects productivity, innovation, sustainability, and overall economic growth (Equileap, 2021). Nonetheless, emerging evidence confirms that when women are given equal opportunities, they make significant contributions to economic development (Sri-Guran et al., 2024; Malima, 2024). Thus, gender-equitable and

inclusive succession planning is vital to ensuring that women can ascend to leadership roles across all levels of business. This includes intentionally creating pathways for women with business and management training to lead, particularly within family-owned enterprises.

Globally, SMEs represent about 90% of all businesses, employ 60–70% of the workforce, and contribute approximately 50% of global GDP (Akpan & Ukpai, 2017). SMEs play a crucial role in local and national economies, supporting livelihoods particularly for the working poor, women, youth, and other vulnerable groups. In sub-Saharan Africa, SMEs make up 95% of registered businesses and contribute around 50% to GDP (Muriithi, 2017). In Tanzania, SMEs contribute one-third of the GDP and generate about 40% of total employment (URT, 2012). Nevertheless, despite these statistics, women's participation in SMEs remains significantly lower than that of men (Veckalne et al., 2023), partly due to systemic barriers within the education system. Limited access to business, financial, and leadership education for women and girls continues to hinder their ability to participate fully and competitively in SME development and leadership.

Despite recognizing the contribution of SMEs to economic growth and community development in Tanzania, it is still unclear to what extent gender-equitable succession planning for SMEs has been prioritized. How many women are in leadership positions in those few businesses where they are involved, meaning receiving inheritance based on a succession plan? Previous research has provided different perspectives and methodologies to enhance the effectiveness of succession planning (Olowoyeye, 2019; Wang et al., 2018). However, there is a lack of empirical research on the impact of gender-equitable succession planning on the sustainability of SMEs in Tanzania. According to Essien (2022) and Gwakwa (2020), succession planning in SMEs should be integrated into the organization's broader strategic plan to ensure efficient and sustainable business operations that ultimately benefit the owners. In this context, it is crucial to highlight the importance of a gender-equitable succession plan and the involvement of both genders in SMEs. This study aims to evaluate the role of gender equity in succession planning practices for SMEs in Tanzania.

2. Methodology

A mixed-method research design was employed in this study to combine the breadth of quantitative data with the depth of qualitative insights, enabling a more comprehensive understanding of gender-equitable succession planning in Tanzanian SMEs. The study was conducted in the Kahama District involving Kahama Municipality, Ushetu, and Msalala Districts Councils in Shinyanga Region, chosen for its growth in commercial activities such as mining, agriculture, rice and paddy trade, and private sector investments (URT, 2020). The respondents included 50 registered SME owners from various sectors such as construction, transport, agriculture, mining, and mixed business traders obtained from their regional business associations. The study focused on SME owners as the sampling unit. Purposive sampling techniques were used to select them for interviews.

A cross-sectional research design was utilized to gather both quantitative and qualitative data. Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) were conducted for qualitative data, while semi-structured questionnaires were employed for quantitative data collection. In this study, FGDs were conducted alongside KIIs to capture comprehensive and context-specific insights. The use of FGDs allowed for the exploration of shared experiences, collective views, and community dynamics among SME owners, while KIIs provided expert opinions and policy-related perspectives from individuals with specialized knowledge of the SMEs sector. Employing both methods ensured triangulation of data, thereby enhancing the reliability and depth of the findings. Gender equity indicators including knowledge, participation, rights, norms, and values for SMEs were identified based on the criteria outlined by ILO (2022) and Belingheri et al. (2021).

Descriptive statistical analysis was employed to examine sample characteristics, assess the status of SME succession planning practices and gender equity for SMEs, and examine the attitude of SME owners on gender-equitable succession planning practices. Data were collected using a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree, and 5 = strongly agree). Furthermore, the construct validity was measured statistically using Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). The data analysis involved calculating the mean and standard deviation for each Likert scale item to summarize the central tendencies and variability of responses. SPSS statistical software was used for this analysis. The qualitative data were analyzed using content analysis.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Characteristics of the sampled population

Table 1 provides statistical analysis of the sample characteristics based on variables such as age, sex, marital status, education level, type of business, and years of operation and business ownership. Table 1 indicates that the highest number of SME respondents (60%) came from Kahama MC, with the least respondents (20%) from Ushetu DC and Msalala DC respectively. Kahama MC recorded the highest number of respondents as Kahama is one of the very unique business districts in Shinyanga region due to its rapid economic growth spanning from Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME), agriculture enterprises, and mining (URT, 2020).

Table 1. Statistical analysis of the sample characteristics (n =50).

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent (%)
Municipality/District Council	Ushetu	10	20
	Msalala	10	20
	Kahama	30	60
Age	20 to 29 years	10	20
	30 to 39 years	15	30
	40 to 49 years	15	30
	50 and over	10	20
Sex	Male	30	60
	Female	20	40
Marital Status	Married	30	60
	Single	5	10
	Widow/er	10	20
	Separated	5	10
Level of Education	Primary Education	20	40
	Secondary Education	15	30
	University/Collage	8	16
	Other	7	12
Type of business	Agriculture	5	10
	Transportation	5	10
	Mixed business traders	20	40
	Mining	15	30
	Construction	5	10
Operational Years	Less than 5 years	20	40
	Between 5 & 10 years and over	30	60
Ownership	Single Owner	10	20
	Family Business	30	60
	Co-ownership	10	20

Source: Field data (2024)

Table 1 also indicates that the majority of respondents (30%) were aged 30-39, with another 30% falling in the 40-49 age range. This suggests that the active working population for SMEs typically ranges from 30 to 49 years old. The survey also revealed that 60% of the respondents were male, while 40% were female, indicating a higher male representation in SMEs, as supported by UN Women (2021). Moreover, most of the respondents were married, reflecting the family-oriented nature of businesses in the study. In terms of education, 40% of respondents had primary edu-

Education, 30% had secondary education, and 16% had university/college education, with the remaining 14% having other types of training. This highlights that a significant number of SME owners have basic education.

Additionally, 40% of respondents were engaged in mixed business trading and mining activities. Regarding the age of the businesses surveyed, 60% had been operating for 5 to 10 years, while 40% had been in business for less than 5 years. Lastly, the majority of businesses had a family-based ownership structure, with 60% owned by families, 10% by single owners, and 10% by co-owners. This aligns with the findings of Astrachan & Shanker (2003), which also support the prevalence of family-owned businesses.

3.2 Status of the succession planning practices and gender equity for SMEs

The objective was to evaluate how SME owners address gender equity issues in their businesses. Indicators such as knowledge, leadership, participation, resources, rights, norms, and values, as identified by ILO (2020) and Belingheri et al. (2021), were used.

Findings in Figure 1 show that 42% of the respondents preferred male successors to take leadership roles in SMEs, while only 10% preferred female successors. One female respondent noted that "...Inheritance of leadership to female children in business is difficult. Customs and traditions dictate that a female child will get married and start a new family. It is challenging to make her a leader when there are male children who are given priority to manage the family business" (Participant, FDG, 2024).

The above findings indicate that SMEs prioritize men over women in succession planning, resulting in limited opportunities for women. According to Abiri & Olugasa (2022), a male-dominated system persists in business leadership, favouring men due to cultural norms. Therefore, it is important to note that promoting gender equality in business and innovation can benefit both society and the economy by creating opportunities for women entrepreneurs and driving social and technological progress (World Bank, 2022). Achieving this, however, requires a strong foundation in education, particularly in entrepreneurship and technology, to equip women and girls with the skills, knowledge, and confidence needed to participate fully in innovative and competitive business environments.

Figure 1. Status of the Succession Planning practices and gender equity for SMEs (n =50).

Key Note: 1 = Preference for male successors, 2 = Preference for female successors, 3 = Inadequate awareness about succession planning, 4 = Absence of succession planning practices, 5 = Lack of consideration for gender equity in succession planning.

Source: Field Research (2024)

The findings in Figure 1 reveal that 26% of the respondents were unaware of succession planning, 11% did not implement succession planning practices in their businesses, and 11% did not consider gender equity in succession planning for SMEs. These results suggest that gender-equitable succession planning is not a priority among SMEs in the study area, with a lack of awareness and strategies among SME owners. This poses a significant challenge in the business sector, as highlighted in a study by Abiri et al. (2022) on the obstacles faced by women in business. While women are occasionally included in succession planning, there is a critical need to ensure gender diversity is adequately addressed. Research by Wang et al. (2022); Franzke et al. (2022) and Franco et al., (2023) underscores the importance of gender considerations in entrepreneurship, as different genders bring unique characteristics and outcomes. Their findings suggest that the absence of gender-equitable succession planning for SMEs can lead to nega-

tive consequences, such as unexpected business failures and financial losses for families and the economy. Urgent improvements are necessary to address this issue.

3.3 Attitude of SMEs owners on gender equitable succession planning practices.

The findings presented in Table 2 display the attitudinal statements of SME owners regarding gender-equitable succession planning practices, based on responses collected using a Likert scale. These results were further supported by insights from the respondents.

Two descriptive statistics were employed in fulfilling this objective. Firstly, an attempt was made to examine respondents' level of agreement to the variables/statements posing the attitude. Secondly, the summaries of responses were provided using the mean and the standard deviations.

Table 2 presents the responses of SME owners regarding their attitudes towards gender-equitable succession planning practices using a five-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 =Neutral, 4 =Agree, 5 =Strongly Agree). The results were analysed based on mean and standard deviation.

The data in Table 2 indicates that the development of female successors and male-dominated decision-making both exceeded 50%. A majority (54%) strongly agree that there is minimal effort in retaining, nurturing, and developing female successors, highlighting a gender equity gap. These findings reveal the presence of gender inequality in succession planning systems within SMEs. Moreover, 60% agree that decisions in family businesses are typically male dominated, suggesting a cultural barrier to gender equity in succession planning.

Table 2. Attitude of SMEs owners on succession planning practices (n =50).

Variable/Statement	SD(1)	D(2)	N(3)	A(4)	SA(5)	Mean	SD
Lack of knowledge about gender equitable succession planning	10 (20%)	5 (10%)	8 (16%)	10 (10%)	17 (34%)	3.58	1.51
Succession planning considered only during crises	5 (10%)	5 (10%)	5 (10%)	15 (30%)	20 (40%)	4.10	1.22
Female family members not involved	5 (10%)	5 (10%)	0 (10%)	15 (30%)	25 (40%)	4.60	1.40
Little thought given to leadership challenges	5 (10%)	2 (4%)	5 (10%)	15 (30%)	23 (46%)	3.90	1.14
Family members may lack interest in business	10 (20%)	10 (20%)	5 (10%)	10 (20%)	20 (40%)	2.90	1.34
Little effort in developing female successors	2 (4%)	3 (6%)	5 (10%)	13 (26%)	27 (54%)	3.88	1.24
Male-dominated decision-making system	15 (30%)	15 (30%)	5 (10%)	5 (10%)	10 (10%)	2.60	0.96
Family members' successors may lack interest	20 (40%)	10 (20%)	5 (10%)	10 (20%)	5 (10%)	2.90	1.34
Patriarchal system opposes women in leadership	10 (20%)	5 (10%)	5 (10%)	10 (20%)	20 (40%)	2.90	1.34
Importance of gender equity in succession planning	5 (10%)	5 (10%)	0 (0%)	15 (30%)	25 (50%)	4.60	1.40

Note: SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, N = Neutral, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree

Source: Field Research (2024)

These results are consistent with a study by Abiri et al. (2022) in Nigeria, which identifies the exclusion of women in succession planning of family businesses due to cultural and religious beliefs, gender bias, patriarchy, low self-esteem, and incompetence. Korang et al. (2021) and Saan et al. (2018) emphasize that the exclusion of women from family businesses can hinder the sustainability of SMEs, highlighting the importance of addressing gender bias and patriarchal systems in succession planning.

Similarly, the importance of the gender equity statement in Table 2 also scored above 50%, indicating strong agreement among respondents on the significance of considering gender equity in succession planning. One respondent emphasized the significance of gender issues, stating, "Gender issues are important and should not be ignored. They contribute to meaning and equality within families, and all children have the right to lead, including in the business realm. However, the challenge lies in the fact that these issues are often misunderstood." (KII, Female SME Owner, 2024). This demonstrates a recognition of the issue despite existing biases. Olabode (2023) and Orser et al. (2011), suggests that practical solutions for a sustainable family business model are necessary to address these challenges through effective succession planning while considering the gender-based impact on family business performance.

Furthermore, the results in Table 2 generally show that the mean scores for most statements related to succession planning are above 3, indicating a generally positive attitude. However, the variability in responses suggests differing opinions among SME owners. High mean scores were observed for female family members not involved (4.60) and the importance of gender equity in succession planning (4.60), indicating a recognition of gender equity issues but also acknowledge a lack of involvement of female family members in succession planning. These findings show a willingness among family business owners to address and improve the issues.

Mean scores below 3 indicated disagreement and neutrality, particularly in relation to the male-dominated decision-making system (2.60) and family members' interest in the business (2.90), suggesting that traditional gender roles and family interests are perceived as hindrances in succession planning. The consistently low scores for statements on family members' involvement and patriarchal systems emphasize the need for further improvement. One respondent emphasized the urgent need for substantial changes to achieve gender equality, particularly in the context of family businesses. They stated, "We need significant changes to achieve gender equality even in family businesses. The key is to ensure that harmful traditions have no place in our lives, including in business." (KII, Female SME Owner, 2024). This statement highlights the need to challenge traditional practices that impede progress towards equality. Participants emphasize the importance of actively addressing and dismantling harmful practices to create a more inclusive environment. Simply acknowledging gender disparities is not enough; proactive steps are necessary to create change in personal and professional settings. In a study conducted by Duran & Rivas (2022) on Gender Roles and Succession Planning in Family Firms from a Latin American perspective, the findings revealed a mean score of 2.85. This score indicates a perception of male dominance in decision-making within family firms, influenced by traditional norms and practices. These results highlight the persistent challenges associated with traditional gender roles that require attention and action.

Moreover, the standard deviations (ranging from approximately 0.96 to 1.51) indicate the variability in responses. Lower standard deviations (e.g., 0.96 for the male-dominated system) suggest consensus among respondents, whereas higher standard deviations (1.51 for lack of knowledge about gender-equitable succession planning) imply diverse opinions or uncertainty among SME owners about their knowledge in this area. This variability highlights differing levels of awareness and attitudes within the SME owner population.

Generally, the findings indicate that although there is recognition of the significance of gender equity in succession planning, many SME owners continue to adhere to traditional frameworks that restrict female participation and leadership. However, cultural norms and traditional gender roles continue to shape decision-making in some businesses, limiting full adoption of equitable practices. Insights from key informants highlighted that younger SME owners tend to be more open to merit-based succession, often influenced by exposure to modern education, mentorship, and professional development opportunities.

This suggests that structured educational programs, mentorship schemes, and hands-on experiences can play a transformative role in shifting attitudes and practices. These findings align with principles of experiential learning, where individuals develop understanding and skills through reflection on direct experiences. These findings are consistent with Meroño-Cerdán (2023) and Henry et al., (2015), who emphasize the need to increase awareness, provide training, and implement proactive succession planning strategies that prioritize gender equity to promote a more inclusive approach in family-owned businesses.

4. Conclusion and recommendations

Based on the findings, it is concluded that there are substantial obstacles to achieving gender-equitable succession planning in SMEs. These challenges stem from entrenched traditional structures that limit women's access to leadership positions and favour male leadership. SME owners often lack knowledge about succession planning methods and fail to consider gender issues when grooming future business leaders. While acknowledging the significance of gender equality in succession planning, SME owners struggle to involve women due to prevailing male-dominated norms, impeding efforts to promote gender equity. Overcoming these cultural barriers and implementing tailored approaches could enhance the inclusivity of succession planning in SMEs moving forward.

To promote gender equality in family-owned businesses, it is crucial for the government and stakeholders to implement educational programs focused on gender-equitable succession planning for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). These initiatives should aim to raise awareness, develop skills, and foster attitudes that emphasize the strategic benefits of succession planning and the societal importance of gender equality in business leadership. By integrating this content into business development curricula, entrepreneurship training, and mentorship programs, a

culture of gender sensitivity and inclusive decision-making can be cultivated. Furthermore, to advance gender equality in family-owned SMEs, all relevant stakeholders should prioritize educational initiatives that promote gender-equitable succession planning. This can be achieved through public awareness campaigns, mentorship programs, and practical, hands-on learning experiences. Integrating gender equity practices early in SME development supported by financial incentives such as training grants and diversity-focused funding can foster inclusive leadership and contribute to sustainable business growth. Policies should also support gender-equitable succession planning in SMEs to promote inclusive economic growth in Tanzania. This includes integrating gender considerations into national SME strategies, promoting inclusive management training, and challenging cultural norms limiting women's leadership. Ensuring women have equal opportunities in business succession will enhance business sustainability and contribute to national development.

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